

PROSPECTS OF SIMULATIONS AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATIONS OF ELECTROCHEMICAL TREATMENT OF TURBID WATER

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ABSTRACT

Conventional water treatment processes utilised to remove pollutants from wastewaters produce large quantities of hazardous sludge and solid wastes that must be handled, treated, and disposed of, which increase processes costs. The electrochemical treatment of water and wastewaters is an alternative treatment method that efficiently removes these pollutants from wastewaters. This study focuses on models of the overall performance of electrochemical treatment processes in removing selected pollutants from turbid water, which originated from Opa dam. Turbid water samples were collected from Opa dam and subjected to electrochemical treatment using Al-Al electrodes. Data on individual performance were collected from previous study. Overall performance was calculated geometrically. Overall performance of the system was used to evaluate three (3) different models that relates performance to the selected factors and their interactions using Microsoft Excel Solver (MES) and Microsoft Excel Data Analysis (MEDA) function techniques. The performance of these three models was evaluated statistically (Analysis of Variance, regression statistics and simulated the performance). The study revealed that the overall performance was between 32.32 % and 50.75 %, mean of 40.31 %, standard deviation of 5.04 skewness of 0.31 and kurtosis of 0.12. There was a significant difference between the models. Model 3 has regression coefficient square standard error and regression coefficient of 0.9593, 0.389 and 0.9794, respectively. It was concluded that model 3 performed better than model 2 and model 2 performance was better than model 1 based on the values of regression coefficient square, standard error and regression coefficient.

Keywords: Conventional processes, Water treatment, Turbid water, Overall performance, Microsoft Excel Data Analysis, Simulation

INTRODUCTION

Water resources are essential for the development of human society. Water is used for household requirements, industrial and agricultural production, and electricity generation (Bamoso *et al.*, 2021; Karnwal *et al.*, 2024; Feng *et al.*, 2024). Water utilisation has grown worldwide in the past three or four decades, more than twice the population growing rate due to country's level of development, urbanisation and population growth (Gbandi, 2022; Samaraweera *et al.*, 2024). Subsequently, human activities that utilise water produce and generate wastewaters, which pollute the available fresh water resources. With the speedy development of social economy and the constant advancement of urbanization process, the delinquent of water and land environment pollution in world has become progressively prominent. Currently, the growing demand for fresh water is resulting in an upsurge in the quantity of

wastewater produced and discharged worldwide. In relation to sanitation and hygiene, an adequate water supply in suitable quantity and quality has to be guaranteed in societies under all situations and in a unremitting pattern (Salameh, 2022). Therefore, wastewater treatment is becoming critically important and essential to achieve this environmental role of adequate water supply. Conventional processes utilised to remove pollutants from wastewaters produce large quantities of hazardous sludge and solid wastes that must be handled, treated, and disposed of, which increase processes costs. The electrochemical treatment of water and wastewaters is an alternative treatment method that efficiently removes these pollutants from wastewaters. Figure 1 presents the types of electrochemical treatment of water and wastewaters. Figure 2 shows the priorities and challenges of electrochemical treatment of water and wastewaters.

Further information such as types of electrodes, performance, mode and arrangement of electrodes during electrochemical treatment of water and wastewaters can be established in literature such as Feldberg (1987); Sawata (1990) ; Bernard *et al.* (2009); Martinez-Delgado *et al.* (2012); Shi and Ju (2015); Ike *et al.* (2017) ; Shimura *et al.* (2017); Rodríguez *et al.* (2018); Kannan *et al.* (2019) ; Mahanta *et al.* (2019) ; Douche *et al.* (2020) ; Tsai *et al.* (2020) ; Xie and Wang (2020); Xu *et al.* (2020); Yang *et al.* (2020) ; dos Santos *et al.* (2021); Li *et al.* (2023); da Cruz Santana Neves, *et al.* (2023) ; Zhang *et al.* (2021) ; Yaqub *et al.* (2017) ; Qin *et al.* (2023); Tognia *et al.* (2023); Chu *et*

electrochemical models to simulate the performance of electrochemical treatment process, the evaluation of the model with regards to experimental results and strong correlations between the electrochemical treatment process and the electrochemical performance in the degradation of pollutants in the environment. Modeling and simulation are playing an increasingly significant role in effective and safe design for such as electrochemical treatment process and its applications. Modeling and performance simulation of electrochemical treatment process by computation techniques have been increasing during the last fifteen years (Hubler, 2012 ; Rucci *et al.*, 2019; Trembacki *et al.*, 2019 ;

Figure 1: Types of Electrochemical Treatment of Water and Wastewaters (Garcia-Segura *et al.*, 2020)

al. (2024) and Hao *et al.* (2024). From figure 2 there are numerous challenges to overcome before the usage electrochemical treatment processes (Chaplin, (2014); Darvishmotevalli *et al.*, 2019; Garcia-Segura *et al.*, 2020 ; Awfa *et al.*, 2021; Arab *et al.*, 2022; Bian *et al.*, 2023; Abbasi and Moghadam, 2023; Chianeh *et al.*, 2024 and Chu *et al.*, 2024). These challenges include improvement in electrode performance to further enhance the conversion efficiency and reliability, the computational time needed to solve electrochemical treatment process of water and wastewaters, online applications to develop a simplified science (chemistry-physics)-based model, rigorous

Shimura *et al.*, 2019; Garcia-Rodriguez *et al.*, 2022; Zhu *et al.*, 2022; Zaki *et al.*, 2023 ; Ganthavee *et al.*, 2024; Ganthavee and Trzcinski, 2024; Hao *et al.*, 2024 ; Jiang *et al.*, 2024 ; Zhou *et al.*, 2024). The need to improve the performance of existing electrochemical treatment process or the development of new (hybrid) technologies through modeling and performance simulation of electrochemical treatment process has attracted the attention of the scientific community (Sun *et al.*, 2023; Taoufik *et al.*, 2022; Warren-Vega *et al.*, 2024; Yang *et al.*, 2022; Kumar *et al.*, 2024; Li *et al.*, 2024 ; Litrico *et al.*, 2017; Millán *et al.*, 2020 ; Promphet *et al.*, 2024; Puri *et al.*, 2024; Radjenovic and

Figure 2: Priorities and Challenges of Electrochemical Treatment of Water and Wastewaters (Garcia-Segura *et al.*, 2020)

Sedlak, 2015; Regalado-Méndez *et al.*, 2023; Rumky *et al.*, 2024; Shirkoohi *et al.*, 2022; Silva Ferreira, 2024; Singh *et al.*, 2024 ; Son *et al.*, 2021). The main objectives of this study are to develop models that can predict the overall performance electrochemical treatment process in removing selected pollutants from turbid water at Opa dam.

METHODOLOGY

The materials and method used in the study are as stated in previous study (Abah *et al.*, 2024). The performance data were obtained from the study. The data was used to determine overall performance as geometric performance (equation 1) and the coefficients for the three models (simple linear model tagged model 1 and polynomial or interaction model tagged models 2 and 3) using both Microsoft Excel Solver (MES) and Microsoft Excel Data Analysis (MEDA, in-built Microsoft function). Statistical parameters such as minimum, maximum, mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis were determined using standard methods and formulae. Overall efficacy of the system was computed using geometric mean of the system for all the pollutants as follows:

$$P_{all} = \left(\prod_{i=1}^N P(x_i) \right)^{\frac{1}{N}} \quad (1)$$

Where P_{all} is the overall performance, $P(x_i)$ is the performance of factor i , N is the total number of factors and Π is the product symbol. The three models (model 1, model 2 and model 3) are as follows (equations 2, 3 and 4):

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 \quad (2)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_1 X_2 + \beta_6 X_1 X_3 + \beta_7 X_1 X_4 + \beta_8 X_2 X_3 + \beta_9 X_2 X_4 + \beta_{10} X_3 X_4 \quad (3)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_1 X_2 + \beta_6 X_1 X_3 + \beta_7 X_1 X_4 + \beta_8 X_2 X_3 + \beta_9 X_2 X_4 + \beta_{10} X_3 X_4 + \beta_{11} X_1 X_2 X_3 + \beta_{12} X_1 X_2 X_4 + \beta_{13} X_1 X_3 X_4 + \beta_{14} X_2 X_3 X_4 \quad (4)$$

Where β ($\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_k$), $\beta \in \beta$, is the unknown value or constant. β is in general vector value and let $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$ be a recognition of the randomly selected water quality parameters. The flow charts, which explained the procedure for the utilizations of the two techniques are as presented in Figures 3 and 4. These models were evaluated statistically using Analysis of variance (ANOVA), correlation coefficient and coefficient of determination.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results from this study are presented as follows:

Performance of the System (Electrochemical treatment of Turbid Water):

Table 1 presents individual and computed overall performance of the system. The Table established that the overall performance was between 32.32 % and 50.75 %, mean of 40.31 %, standard deviation of 5.04 skewness of 0.31 and kurtosis of 0.12. These results revealed that overall performance is a platykurtic distribution, which has a

kurtosis value less than 3, has thinner tails and a flatter peak compared to a normal distribution and fewer extreme values and a more spread-out distribution of data points. The skewness is positive, which indicates that the distribution has a long tail on the right side (toward higher values), data points are concentrated on the left (lower values), with fewer extreme values on the right and mean is typically greater than the median. Table 2 shows the ANOVA of these individual performances. Table 2 confirmed that there is no significant difference between the experiments at 95 %, but there is significant difference between the performance of the system in respect of the parameters.

Regression Statistics

Table 3 shows information and data on regression statistics (regression coefficient square, standard error and regression coefficient). The Table revealed that regression coefficient square, standard error and regression coefficient for models 1, 2 and 3 are 0.376198, 0.149361 and 0.61335; 0.885678, 0.657034 and 0.941105; and 0.959264, 388965 and 0.97942, which indicates that model 3 performance was greater than the performance of model 2, and performance of model 2 was better than performance of model 1 based on regression statistics. These results revealed that interactions of these selected factor have a vital role in the models. Model 1 without any interaction could not predict the experimental results like model 2 with 2-level interactions and model 3 with 2-level and 3-level interactions. Table 4 presents ANOVA of the regression statistics. The Table established that there is a significant

difference between the models at 95% confidence level ($F_{2,9}$ of 4.268 and p of 0.050).

ANOVA of the Model

Tables 5, 6 and 7 shows information and data on the significance of the three models. The Tables revealed that the significance F (probability) for models 1, 2 and 3 are 0.228964, 0.074052 and 0.546505 respectively. The Tables revealed that the residual (values with higher errors) for models 1, 2 and 3 are 11, 5 and 1, respectively. These results established that model 3 provided the least residual of 1 out of 15 data points, model 2 provided 5 residual out of 15 data points (33.33 %) and model 1 provided 11 residual out of 15 data points.

Model's Constants, Probability and t-Statistics

Table 8 shows information and data on model's constants, probability and t-Statistics. The model's constants revealed

Table 1: The Performance of the Electrochemical Treatment and its Statistical Parameters

Experiment	Vol(A)ML	Time (B)min	Speed(C) cm	Current (D) A	Turbidity	TDS	Chloride	Zinc	Copper	Lead	Cadmium	Overall performance	
1	1.6	15	1.0	0.5	43.9	76.3	66.73	71.56	19.53	15.45	7.63	32.32	
2	1.6	30	1.2	1.0	43.7	64.74	94.41	67.91	22.66	19.95	5.17	32.97	
3	1.6	45	1.5	2.0	43.31	72.54	69.58	51.49	20.88	45.64	19.1	41.30	
4	1.6	60	2.0	3.0	43.85	58.35	52.59	56.85	24.22	28.35	31.99	40.15	
5	1.75	15	1.2	2.0	43.56	67.36	67.02	76.32	23.26	41.99	17.53	42.66	
6	1.75	30	1.0	3.0	43.8	68.95	86.07	42.43	16.66	17.78	43.32	39.17	
7	1.75	45	2.0	0.5	42.73	68.91	66.22	20.4	21.44	28.7	32.41	36.06	
8	1.75	60	1.5	1.0	42.63	76.00	42.33	27.25	20.8	41.73	16.84	34.19	
9	2.0	15	1.5	3.0	43.17	74.38	83.26	71.42	22.15	22.03	28.33	42.82	
10	2.0	30	2.0	2.0	43.12	71.49	61.13	65.53	25.53	51.49	37.65	48.28	
11	2.0	45	1.0	1.0	43.56	80.85	75.78	44.44	24.8	40.74	28.19	44.35	
12	2.0	60	1.2	0.5	43.41	75.04	58.82	34.00	22.2	45.83	22.38	39.43	
13	2.5	15	2.0	1.0	43.22	66.74	74.42	22.25	20.47	52.53	40.35	41.36	
14	2.5	30	1.5	0.5	47.91	61.89	65.75	43.14	15.77	26.72	53.02	40.79	
15	2.5	45	1.2	3.0	48.2	51.76	71.82	32.45	20.4	24.74	41.35	38.32	
16	2.5	60	1.0	2.0	42.88	63.94	58.31	89.35	27.99	46.84	46.11	50.72	
Minimum					42.63	51.76	42.33	20.40	15.77	15.45	5.17	32.32	
Maximum					48.20	80.85	94.41	89.35	27.99	52.53	53.02	50.72	
Mean					43.93	68.70	68.39	51.05	21.80	34.41	29.46	40.31	
Standard Deviation					1.65	7.48	12.93	21.01	3.10	12.66	13.89	5.04	
Skewness						2.25	-0.61	0.11	0.15	-0.10	-0.05	-0.17	0.31
Kurtosis						4.12	0.37	0.41	-1.08	0.45	-1.59	-0.78	0.12

Table 2: ANOVA Results of the Performance of the System

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-value	P-value	F critical at 95 % confidence level
Between the Experiment	1985.088	15	132.3392	1.0037	0.457231	1.762656
Within the Parameters	32963.68	7	4709.097	35.71518	4.65 x 10 ⁻²⁵	2.098005
Error	13844.4	105	131.8514			
Total	48793.16	127				

that the factors and their interactions can be grouped into two as follows:

- a) factors and interactions with negative influence (constants are less than zero) of the performance. These are the factors and interactions with increase in their values reduce or decline the performance of the system, and
- b) factors and interactions with positive influence (constants are greater than zero) of the performance. These are the factors and interactions with increase in their values improved or increased the performance of the system.

The probabilities (p-value) of the constants were between 0.031 (model 1) and 0.945 (model 2). A low p-value (less than 0.05 is a common threshold) indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected, which indicates that there is evidence that the coefficient is significantly different from zero. This means or indicates that the predictor variable is likely to have a real impact on the dependent variable. A high p-value (greater than 0.05) shows that the null hypothesis can be accepted, meaning or indicating that there isn't enough evidence to conclude that the coefficient is different from zero. In this situation, the predictor variable may not have a statistically significant effect on the dependent variable.

The values of t-statistics were between -2.915 (model 1) and 2.464 (model 2). The magnitude of the t-statistic, whether negative or positive, indicates the distance of the observed value is from the hypothesized value in units of

Table 3: Regression Statistics

Coefficients	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Multiple Regression	0.61335	0.941105	0.97942
Regression Square	0.376198	0.885678	0.959264
Standard Error	0.149361	0.657034	0.388965
Regression	0.61335	0.941105	0.97942

standard error. A negative t-statistic indicates that the estimated coefficient or difference between means is below the hypothesized value (usually zero). This indicated that the model's mean is less than the model's mean. In addition, the sign and magnitude of the t-statistic help in the determination of the direction of the differences. A negative t-statistic suggests that the observed value is less than the hypothesized value under the null hypothesis. The t-statistic-value of these models is a mixture of both negative and positive with an indicate of the significant and influence of the factors and interactions.

Predicted Overall Performance

Figure 5 presents predicted overall performance and experimental overall performance of the three models using MES and MEDA techniques. The Figure revealed that in all cases model 3 predicted overall performance than model 2 and model 2 predicted better than model 1. In respect of the techniques MES predicted better than MEDA. Table 9 shows the result of ANOVA for the predicted overall performance using the two techniques. These results indicate that the two can be used as there is no significant difference between the techniques at a 95 % confidence level.

Figure 3: Flow Chart for Utilization of Microsoft Excel Data Analysis Function

Figure 4: Flow Chart for Utilization of Microsoft Excel Solver Function

Table 4: ANOVA of Regression Statistics

Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-value	P-value
Between Models	0.435	2	0.218	4.268	0.050
Within Models	0.459	9	0.051		
Total	0.895	11			

Table 5: Significant of Model 1

	Degree of freedom	Sum of Square	Mean Sum of Square	F-value	Significance F
Regression	4	143.5339	35.88347	1.658449	0.228964
Residual	11	238.0044	21.63676		
Total	15	381.5382			

Table 6: Significant of Model 2

	Degree of freedom	Sum of Square	Mean Sum of Square	F-value	Significance F
Regression	10	337.92	33.792	3.873609	0.074052
Residual	5	43.61824	8.723648		
Total	15	381.5382			

Table 7: Significant of Model 3

	Degree of freedom	Sum of Square	Mean Sum of Square	F-value	Significance F
Regression	14	365.996	26.14257	1.682035	0.546505
Residual	1	15.54223	15.54223		
Total	15	381.5382			

Table 8: Model's Constants, Probability and t-Statistics

Model Constants	Model Constants			Probability			t-statistics		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Intercept(β_0)	21.476	-46.055	-216.099	0.031	0.517	0.425	2.464	-0.696	-1.267
β_1	6.997	26.477	140.639	0.064	0.475	0.390	2.056	0.771	1.423
β_2	0.025	-0.058	-1.540	0.728	0.945	0.726	0.357	-0.072	-0.459
β_3	0.879	69.696	138.225	0.781	0.159	0.453	0.285	1.654	1.161
β_4	1.797	14.635	194.363	0.166	0.105	0.393	1.483	1.975	1.411
β_5		0.476	0.955		0.237	0.645		1.342	0.625
β_6		-22.379	-73.807		0.287	0.415		-1.190	-1.312
β_7		-8.737	-110.608		0.033	0.388		-2.915	-1.431
β_8		-0.695	1.898		0.051	0.641		-2.546	0.633
β_9		0.008	-1.002		0.898	0.644		0.135	-0.627
β_{10}		2.377	-110.007		0.371	0.447		0.982	-1.182
β_{11}			-1.216			0.524			-0.927
β_{12}			0.534			0.620			0.680
β_{13}			62.904			0.426			1.265
β_{14}			0.078			0.875			0.198

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that concluded that overall performance was between 32.32 % and 50.75 %, mean of 40.31 %, standard deviation of 5.04 skewness of 0.31 and kurtosis of 0.12. There was a significant difference between the models at 95% confidence level ($F_{2,9}$ of 4.268 and p of 0.050).

Model 3 has regression coefficient square standard error and regression coefficient of 0.9593, 0.389 and 0.9794, respectively. Model 3 performed better than model 2 and model 2 performance was better than model 1 based on the values of regression coefficient square, standard error and regression coefficient. MES and MEDA proved effectively in the simulations. The prospect of the models is high based on model's constants, probability and t-Statistics as well as

Figure 5: Predicted Overall Performance and Experimental Overall Performance of the Three Models using MES and MEDA Techniques.

Table 9: ANOVA Results for Predicted Overall Performance using the Two Techniques

Source of Variation	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Degree of freedom	Mean Sum of Square	F-value	F critical at 95 % confidence level
Between MEDA and MSE	153.153	6	25.5255083	1.196823	0.313804	2.186134
Within MEDA and MSE	2239.411	105	21.3277225			
Total	2392.564	111				

the predicted overall performance and experimental overall performance of the three models using MES and MEDA.

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